

Rubin/LSST In-kind Contribution Program Produces Mutual Benefits

International contributors provide value for Rubin Observatory in return for data rights

Bob Blum, Phil Marshall (SLAC), Kristen Metzger, and Aprajita Verma (University of Oxford) and the In-kind Program Team

Program Overview

The Vera C. Rubin Observatory In-kind Program offers the opportunity for international organizations to obtain Rubin data rights in return for contributions that will enhance the science impact of Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). Launched in 2019, the program spans many varied in-kind contributions providing

resources and support to Rubin Operations and the Rubin Science Community. As of late 2023, the Rubin In-kind Program involves 153 contributions from 43 individual teams from 28 countries, plus the US and Chile. The program is facilitated by the Rubin International Program Coordination (IPC) Team (see Table 1), which reports to the Rubin

Director and Deputy Director of Operations. Now wrapping up its second full year of contribution effort by the participating teams, the program has proven successful by filling needs in the Rubin ecosystem, while meeting the desire for Rubin data rights in the international community, as the observatory gets closer to starting science operations.

Table 1: The Rubin IPC Team

Agnès Ferté (SLAC)	Software contributions and general pool coordination
Greg Madejski (SLAC)	Community Engagement Team Liaison
Steve Margheim (NOIRLab)	Telescope time and dataset contributions (primary contact)
Phil Marshall (SLAC)	Contributions to Rubin, Data Rights Agreements and list (Deputy Director of Operations)
Knut Olsen (NOIR Lab)	Independent Data Access Centers and other computing resources
Stephen Ridgway (NOIRLab)	Telescope time and datasets contributions (secondary contact), NSF's NOIRLab Community Science and Data Center Liaison
Susan Ridgway (NOIRLab)	Software contributions
Aprajita Verma (Oxford)	Software contributions and SC/Recipient Liaison (IPC Team Lead)
Heather M. Shaughnessy (SLAC)	Data rights holder database management, office hours coordination (Program Operations support)
Sierra Villarreal (SLAC)	Independent Data Access Centers technical coordinator

Rubin Data Rights

There will be two types of Rubin data: prompt products, which most notably include the alert stream, and data release products, which will be generated approximately annually. Alerts will be world-public, while the data releases will have a proprietary period of two years, during which they will be available only to people with Rubin data rights. All US and Chilean scientists will have Rubin data rights, as will non-US scientists covered by data rights agreements with the US agencies (or their designates) through this in-kind program. Because Rubin data is poised to revolutionize the fields of astronomy and astrophysics, there is significant desire for data rights agreements from institutions outside the US and Chile.

This model of in-kind participation in Rubin's LSST widens the ways in which international teams can contribute to include time, expertise, and/or access to existing infrastructure of providing for data rights access. The guiding principle set up by NSF and DOE is that these in-kind contributions should benefit the US science enterprise, whether directly related to Rubin and the LSST or not.

Getting off the Ground

The In-kind Program was introduced in the northern fall of 2019 with an invitation to contributing institutions holding MOAs under the previous program, as well as to other groups

that had expressed interest in obtaining Rubin data rights. Contributors were asked to submit Letters of Intent (LOIs) in November, after which the two funding agencies reviewed and confirmed the proposed contribution ideas. Detailed proposals followed in the northern spring of 2020 — contributing organizations were encouraged to work closely with Rubin teams or Science Collaborations to develop their proposals, ensuring that the proposed contributions were well aligned with Rubin needs and contained appropriate mechanisms for ongoing communication and engagement.

Rubin leadership established a special In-kind Contribution Evaluation Committee (CEC) to review these

proposals. The CEC recommended successful proposals, which were then approved by Rubin directors and then formally accepted for further development by NSF and Department of Energy (DOE). As of this writing, the In-kind Program has broad participation from around the world (see Figure 1). While the basic scope of each In-kind Program contribution has been approved by Rubin Observatory, NSF, and DOE, the actual Data Rights Agreements (which are made between either AURA and a program, or SLAC and a program) have not been approved for signature by either NSF or DOE as those agencies make their final review of these formal agreements.

Figure 1: Countries with data rights to the Legacy Survey of Space and Time. Different colors aid in seeing distinct countries with data rights by virtue of an in-kind program, host country (Chile), or lead (USA).

A Range of Contributions

Current in-kind contribution projects span a diverse set of projects that

benefit different elements of the Rubin system, as shown in Figure 2. The financial value of these contributions is significant. The total and relative

amounts per category are shown in Figure 4. How these contributions connect to the LSST Science Collaborations is detailed in Table 2.

Figure 2: Summary of the current Rubin In-kind Program by category

Contribution Lifecycle

After proposal acceptance and agreeing on a start date for the work, each contributor is responsible for setting up a program work plan in liaison with the recipient group; this outlines the work to be done towards the contribution with objectives and milestones. Quarterly updates ensure that progress remains on track, and an annual evaluation gives a holistic view of what was achieved during the prior year. Contribution groups are encouraged to maintain a high level of engagement with the Rubin team or Science Collaboration that is benefiting from their contribution. If lapses in communication or engagement occur, the IPC Team steps in to facilitate. Each individual program of contributions is managed by a local Program Manager (PM) who is responsible to maintain an overview of the status of a program and its constituent contributions, ensuring good communications, progress, and reporting. Participants have access to a suite of [resources](#), including a comprehensive [handbook](#), and the IPC hosts assemblies, about once per quarter, to communicate with stakeholders in an inclusive way.

Example Contributions

The diversity of contributions that have already started are providing valuable returns to the Observatory. For example, the expertise of system engineers from the Italian Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica (INAF) program have been on-site to help with efforts towards commissioning and Systems Verification and Validation. They have been requested to return to the observatory site in FY24. This is

Table 2: Current Contribution Breakdown by Science Collaboration

Primary Recipients	Type	Number of Contributions	Equivalent Value (\$M)
AGN	Telescope Time and Datasets	1	0.1
AGN	Directable SW Effort	7	4.3
DESC	Telescope Time and Datasets	4	2.4
DESC	Non-directable SW Effort	6	3.5
DESC	Directable SW Effort	24	17.3
Galaxies	Non-directable SW Effort	3	2.5
Galaxies	Directable SW Effort	8	4.3
Solar System	Directable SW Effort	2	1.2
SMWLV	Non-directable SW Effort	1	1.2
SMWLV	Directable SW Effort	3	2.0
Strong Lensing	Non-directable SW Effort	1	0.3
Strong Lensing	Directable SW Effort	2	1.6
TVS	Telescope Time and Datasets	3	2.7
TVS	Non-directable SW Effort	3	1.7
TVS	Directable SW Effort	12	10.1
Totals:		80	55.1

part of a substantial committed pool of effort involving US and international teams providing support for commissioning activities to Rubin Observatory. Several contributions involve staff effort provided to Rubin Operations teams, as a way of offsetting the cost to the US funding agencies and broadening international participation in the observatory’s workings. The French Institut National de Physique Nucléaire et de Physique des Particules (IN2P3) and LSST:UK in-kind programs are making major contributions in the areas of data release processing (at the Rubin France and UK Data Facilities) and LSSTCam commissioning and maintenance (following a many-year collaboration between Rubin and the IN2P3 laboratories on the camera’s construction).

As another example, the Korean in-kind program, led by the Korea

Astronomy and Space Science Institute (KASI), is contributing two Observing Specialist postdocs to the nighttime operations team, with the first one entering via a new collaborative KASI-KIPAC Fellowship program. Alongside the other Observing Specialist postdocs, the KASI-KIPAC Fellow will spend two years in Chile troubleshooting the telescope and camera at night and then return to Stanford’s Kavli Institute for Particle Astrophysics and Cosmology (KIPAC) for two years of LSST science research. The fellowship can be rounded out with a final two years at KASI, providing a unique six-year experience for the successful applicant as well as much-needed manpower at the Summit Facility. This fellowship is planned to be duplicated at NSF’s NOIRLab, with the first search for a KASI-NOIRLab Rubin Observing Specialist Fellow tentatively scheduled to start in October 2025.

Preparation for defining additional computational resources (processing and data access) brought in through the international program is well underway. A dedicated workshop held in March 2023 was organized by coordinator Knut Olsen jointly with the UK and Brazilian Independent Data Access Center (IDAC) teams to explore the science use cases that will shape the requirements on the data access and scientific processing centers. The initial program also includes some significant telescope time resources that will be offered and allocated to the US science community through NOIRLab. Coordinator Steve Margheim together with Rachel Street (Las Cumbres Observatory) organized an Observatories Workshop, bringing together the international teams with AEON¹ specialists to help them prepare resources for the time offered, particularly for integration with AEON. Many software contributions have started under the direction of their recipient groups including a community software resource — the General Pool of software experts. Several projects have kicked off to provide varied resources to Rubin and to the Rubin/LSST Science Collaborations that develop infrastructure or tools that enhance elements of the recipient group's

system or pipelines and cover scheduling to science. This is managed by coordinators Agnès Ferté and Aprajita Verma. The opportunity to request effort from the General Pool remains open all year round; please contact the relevant Rubin Recipient Groups if you have a use case for this resource.

Upcoming Plans

The IPC, in conjunction with Rubin leadership, is planning a [targeted expansion](#) of the In-kind Program to meet remaining resource needs in the Rubin community. After specific needs are established, proposals will be

accepted on a rolling basis to match the needs with contributions from existing and prospective groups, including teams in the US and Chile. The NOIRLab community is invited to explore resources (including telescope time and datasets) that might be of value to the US community and follow the same guiding principle as the original In-kind program. These can be proposed through the simple form at ls.st/ikc-rn.

For more information about the Rubin In-kind Program, visit the [program web page](#). The In-kind team can be contacted via jikh@lsst.org.

In-Kind Program Value (\$M) by Category

Figure 3: Distribution and value of currently accepted international in-kind contributions by category

¹AEON (Astronomical Event Observatory Network) is a collaboration between Las Cumbres Observatory and NSF's NOIRLab to support real time follow-up of Rubin or other alerts on a network of telescopes including those run by LCO and NOIRLab (SOAR, Gemini, Blanco initially). See <https://noirlab.edu/public/projects/aeon/>.